

A STUDY OF EXISTING TEACHING STRATEGY FOR GEOGRAPHY SUBJECT AT SECONDARY SCHOOL IN SATARA TALUKA

¹ Pol Uaddhav Vijay, ² Dr. Madhuri Isave

¹Assistant Professor, Vidya Prabodhini College of Commerce, Education, Computer & Management,
Parvati, Goa State. 403521, India.

²Associate Professor, Tilak College of Education Pune. Maharashtra State 411030, India

Abstract:

The purpose of this article is to identify the different types of teaching strategies implemented in secondary school geography lessons in Satara taluka. A questionnaire survey was prepared and distributed among the geography teachers who were teaching geography subject for Std. IX. Forty-two teachers responded to the all the questions, which were asked in the questionnaire survey. The Percentage statistical techniques was used for the analyses and interpretation. As found in the study, very few teachers implement different teaching strategies for teaching geography subject for IXth Std. in their geography lessons. Seventy seven percent of the teachers who responded to the questionnaire did not conduct any field visit activity in geography subject while Twenty three of them implemented an in-school field visit activity at least once a week in an educational year. As the study revealed, geography teachers in Satara taluka started using traditional methods including class discussion, asking and answering questions and using domination the classrooms. The study shows that there is scope of activity-based teaching learning at secondary school for geography lessons. However, its success will depend on how much teachers will adapt themselves to the new developments and how they uses activity based teaching strategies for the Geography subject.

Key Words—Teaching Strategy, Geography, Secondary School.

INTRODUCTION

In 21st century, we can see enormous changes in education due mainly to the advance in science and technology. Traditional teaching and learning methods, which were teacher centered and based mainly on rote learning, have changed into activity based teaching learning process and today's schools in many countries have become places where active learning strategies are practiced. Active learning involves students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing. Many approaches have been developed so far in the frame of active learning such as applied learning, student-cantered learning, cooperative learning, and project-based learning .The placing of students in the centre of learning whilst encouraging teachers to act as guides during the teaching process necessitates the use of activities in learning and teaching, which is commonly referred to as activity-based learning paradigm, in pedagogical parlance.

Activity-based teaching learning means learning by doing and comprises many different in-and out-of-school

activities practiced by students either individually or as a group. Many different activities are implemented in learning and teaching today ranging from role-playing, class discussion and case-study methods to fieldwork, projects and laboratory experiments. Activity-based learning provides students with a wide range of opportunities to gain not only subject knowledge effectively but also many general, technical and academic skills. By interacting with many different learning activities and technologies, students are also prepared as active citizens. Activity-based learning is used extensively in most subject areas around the world, as it is the better instructional method.

Activity-based teaching learning is especially important in secondary school education in the teaching of applied subjects and geography is one of them. Geography is the study of spatial variation, of how and why things differ from place to place on the surface of the earth. It is a broad discipline, which examines the earth from different perspectives by using different tools and methods in its wide range of sub-fields. In higher education, students learn about geography mainly to pursue a career in this discipline. However, the aim of teaching geography in secondary education is to give students necessary knowledge and skills to understand the earth as their home and utilize its resources sustainably during their lifetime. This aim can be achieved by carrying the real life with all its different aspects, tools and concerns into the learning and teaching environment by implementing different activities. Activity-based learning is therefore given a great importance in secondary school geography education.

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

NEP 2020 stresses the active teaching-learning Process. In Indian National Educational Policy 2020, Education promotes Experiential Learning as Active Learning in today's Classrooms. Where Teaching and learning will be conducted in a more interactive manner encouraging questions/dialogue with fun, creative, collaborative, and exploratory activities Pedagogy for active participation of the students to motivate and encourage for the learning.

NEP 2020 also suggests creating a learning environment is important to enrich the learning experiences of students. The teacher should expose learners to the immediate environment which is full of exciting possibilities for creating - learning situations. Such type of instructional design creates better learning experiences with flexibility. Students also learn from past experiences and existing ideas are collated to enrich their learning experiences. Teachers should use different strategies for the teaching-learning environment. Such a type of active engagement strategy requires for the teaching and learning process. To know what are the existing teaching strategies implemented for geography subject by the geography teacher at secondary level the survey was conducted.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To identify the activities implemented for the teaching geography subject at secondary level.
- 2) To know the methods are employed for geography subject at IXth standard.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

For this reason, this study aimed at answering the following research questions:

1. What types of school activities are implemented at IXth standard geography subject for teaching learning process?
2. At what are the methods employed for geography teaching at IXth standard?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

a. Method of research - In this study, survey method was adopted. It involves data collection through questionnaire. Finding were made by analysis of collected data.

b. Population and sample

- 1. Population** –All the teachers who were teaching Geography subject in Marathi medium schools in Satara taluka.
- 2. Sample**- All the Schools were in Satara taluka were divided into urban and rural schools. 8 Schools were selected from urban area and 14 schools were selected from rural area of Satara taluka. In this sampling total 22 schools were included and 42 geography teacher were sample for the present study out of which 23 teachers from rural school and 19 teachers were included from the urban area schools.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A questionnaire was prepared to answer the research questions of the study. Twenty-four questions were asked in the questionnaire.

TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

Questionnaire was made by researcher as a tool for data collection

The tool was used to collect data was questionnaire method. Both the types of Questions were included in the questionnaire that is close end and open ended questions.

The following aspects covered by the questionnaire

1. Organization of different activities for the teaching of geography to IXth std. such as organization of exhibitions , field visits etc. of
2. Establishment of geography club to conduct activities
3. Efforts made by the teachers for active participation of the students
4. Organize the guest lectures of students
5. Different efforts for achieve the goals of geography teaching
6. Methods adopted by the geography teacher
7. Use of teaching aids
8. Reasons for using or not using teaching aids
9. Abilities developed after teaching IXth std. geography etc.
10. Opinion of geography teacher about active engagement of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The questionnaire consisted of a question to know the teachers were organized exhibitions in the school as a teaching learning activity. Twenty Six teachers (62 %) said that they were not able organize exhibitions in the school. Whereas sixteen teachers (38 %) stated that they organized exhibitions in the school as a teaching learning activity for active participation of the students.

The organization of field visits for the students for geography subject. In response to this question Thirty two geography teacher (77 %) stated that they were not able to organized field visits to teach geography teachers whereas Ten teachers (23%) geography teachers were organized field visits as activity for the students in geography subject.

The question was regarding geography club and their activities Thirty nine teachers (93%) stated that they do not have any geography club in their school. Three teachers (7%) response shows that they have teacher geography club in their schools to conduct various activities through the geography club.

Twenty Six geography teachers (62%) stated that they were not able to take active participation of the students while using teaching learning process. Sixteen teachers (38. %) geography teachers they took active participation of students while teaching geography.

The lectures organized of resources persons only Two teachers (5%) stated yes response for organized lectures of resources persons in geography and Forty (95 %) geography teachers were not able to organized lectures for geography subject to create interest among the students through this activity.

Twenty Six geography teachers ask questions, Twenty seven geography teacher conduct map filling activity, Twenty three teachers provide opportunities of observation while teaching and also Twenty one teachers gives activity based home work to the students. But most of geography teachers they were not able to conduct activity for practical geography and not to give sufficient time for reading books related to geography.

One of the question in questionnaire regarding use of teaching method for geography. Thirty (71%) geography teachers used lecture method to teach geography subject. But other methods to use for geography subject by the geography teachers are less than (15%).

Twelve teachers (29 %) geography teachers always used teaching aids to teach geography subject, sixteen geography teachers (38%) often used teaching aids whereas thirteen (31%) geography teachers (31%) sometime they used geography teaching aids to get actively participation of the students in teaching learning activity.

The major reason for not using teaching aids during the teaching learning process is that insufficient teaching aids available in the school. Nineteen geography teachers (45%) do not have sufficient teaching aids in their schools. Twelve teachers (29%) have limited teaching aids in their schools and five teachers (12%) does not skills to use teaching aids for geography subject. Twenty one (50%) geography teachers does not have sufficient time to use teaching aids while teaching learning process.

CONCLUSION

Teachers should also be provided with supplementary materials and an appropriate physical environment to prepare and conduct various activities in their lessons. Conducting activities are important, however, knowing how these activities affect students' learning and success are more important. For this reason, teachers should be able to assess each activity they implement in their lessons. Activity-based teaching learning seems to have gained a momentum for geography subject. However, whether it will be enough to reach the common goals of geography subject depends on how much teachers will force themselves to adapt to the changes and how much support they will get from their schools. Hence there is need some actively engaged teaching strategy or programme to help geography teachers to achieve the objectives of the geography subject.

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